

REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONAL COMPETENCE OF THE LEADER IN THE MANAGEMENT OF A PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION.

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Annotation: in this article, we highlight the main components in the content of the management activities of the head of the preschool educational organization in the process of analyzing approaches and work aimed at developing the personal competence of the leader in the management of the preschool educational organization

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Global changes in the social-economic and scientific and technical spheres of the world are new requirements for the management personnel training system it assumes improvement on the basis of. Improving the content, requirements, character and directions of management and professional activities requires the introduction of new paradigms and competency approaches to the system of training and training of executive personnel.

International pedagogical experiments show that the effectiveness of Management in education, the management competencies and its composition of the leader, in management activities, assumes the improvement of the personal competencies of the leader in order to develop planning, organization, training, upbringing, coordination, sorting, motivation, accounting and control skills.

Today in our country, preschool educational organizations improve the professional knowledge and practical skills of the leadership personnel, the scientific and methodological foundations of the development of management competencies, their qualifications in the field of organization and management of preschool education increasing, as well as improving models for the development of management competencies through the means of innovative educational technologies, is required to carry out scientific research in areas. This indicates that the leaders of preschool organizations need to apply different approaches to increasing their personal competence and their managerial competencies.

Leaders of preschool educational organizations are studying trends aimed at developing professional activities in order to change the directions of modernization. It is necessary to introduce new technologies to develop themselves, to introduce students to innovative features, to work as an independent self-economic organization of the school, to teach "soft skills", which must be taken into account. Great attention is paid to the integration of digital education, social networks and technologies, the great challenge of personal development, the growth of scientific competence and self-development. As a result of these trends, leaders have divided themselves into new innovative technologies, teaching methods and changing and developing worldly information.

During our research, we were convinced of the need to develop personal competence of the directors of preschool educational organizations, using special courses, seminars and digital technologies.

Each leader independently decides whether it is necessary to focus on external and internal factors, realizing the complex requirements for his professional activity and personality.

Theoretical knowledge and managerial abilities, the listed volume of requirements for labor productivity require a certain level of professional competence from the head of the preschool educational organization.

In the process of analyzing the work, we highlight the main components in the content of the management activities of the head of the preschool educational organization:

1) informational and analytical.

Organizes the formation (collection, analysis, processing, storage) of information on the main blocks;

2) motivational-purposeful.

Together with all public organizations in accordance with the real conditions for the development of preschool educational organizations, it forms the goals on the basis of social order;

3) Planning and forecasting.

Together with Methodists, the Supervisory Board of the preschool organization, community organizations, it forecasts the zones of close development of the preschool

organization as a whole, some groups of children and educators. Carries out coordination of activities for the implementation of the plan;

4) organizational and executive.

The preschool educational organization provides general guidance on the optimization of the activities of the management apparatus on the basis of periodic and chronograms and the organization's work plan;

5) Control and evaluation.

Exercises control over all the main activities of the preschool organization

6) regulatory and corrective (operational - functional regulation).

Provides regulation and correction at the level of the plan (program) established in all areas of activity of the preschool educational organization, eliminates deviations both in the process itself and among its participants.

All of the above facts make it possible to draw a number of conclusions on the new functionality of the head of the preschool educational organization.

Currently, the search for ways to increase the capabilities and resources of each leader, taking into account the socio-psychological characteristics, should become the main task of Educational Management and a decisive condition for increasing the effectiveness of the activities of the educational organization.

